

Midterm Challenges and Achievements 2024–2025 Biennium

Alejandro Molina-López^{1, 2}

Commentary

Volume 5, Issue 1, January–April 2025

Molina-López, 2025

doi: XXXXXX/XX.XXXX-XXX.2025.02

Affiliations

¹Dirección de Servicios Clínicos, Instituto Nacional de Psiquiatría Ramón de la Fuente Muñiz, Ciudad de México, México

²Presidencia, Asociación Psiquiátrica Mexicana, A.C. Ciudad de México, México

Correspondence

Anillo Periférico 4194-104 Jardines del Pedregal. Álvaro Obregón. Zip Code 01900.

México City, México

Contact

(+52) 55 5652-5576

amolinaspresidente@psiquiatriasapm.org.mx

Conflicts of Interest

The author declares no conflicts of interest concerning this publication

Acknowledgments

The author received no financial support or sponsorship for the development of this commentary

Publication Details

Received: 01/20/2025

Accepted: 01/27/2025

Introduction

The 2024–2025 Biennium has reached its midpoint, a period characterized by institutional challenges and advancements for the Asociación Psiquiátrica Mexicana, A.C. In April 2024, Dr. Rafael Medina Dávalos †, Secretary of Publications, passed away. His contributions have been recognized, and his legacy will be continued through the association's editorial and academic initiatives.

Institutional Developments

In this context, the association has prioritized a range of professional and academic projects to foster participation from active members and psychiatry trainees. One such endeavor is the SALMER-CARE Project (Cuidado y Atención al Médico Residente, due to its Spanish abbreviations), developed to enhance access to mental health services within national residency curricula and contribute to reducing disparities in treatment access for this population. A two-year strategy was implemented to this end and has achieved its stated goal.

Journal's Editorial Committee

On the other hand, nearly fifty years ago, the Revista de la Asociación Psiquiátrica Mexicana, A.C., was founded. Initially, it was a scientific communication platform under the vision of the late Dr. Ramón de la Fuente Muñiz †. To continue its vision, the association developed a strategic plan to modernize its official scientific publication, ensuring compliance with current international publishing standards. Dr. Francisco R. de la Peña directed the implementation of this goal, with the author of this commentary serving as Editor-in-Chief and Dr. José Carlos Medina-Rodríguez as Associate Editor. An Editorial Committee was formed to execute this objective, undertaking a complete administrative restructuring of the journal's aims, scope, and editorial guidelines. The committee secured the journal's International Standard Serial Number (ISSN 3061-7979) from the International ISSN Centre, providing formal recognition (International ISSN Centre, 2024).

Subsequently, Digital Object Identifiers (DOI) have been assigned to all articles accepted since 2024. This procedure supports standard indexing practices, open science initiatives, and the digital preservation of published works (Crossref, 2024). The journal's indexing in national and international repositories was also initiated. These developments provide researchers in psychiatry, neuroscience, and psychosocial disciplines a platform to publish their findings, with dissemination aligned with global standards.

Literary Editorial Board

With the consolidation of the association's journal, the association also established a Literary Editorial Board under the direction of Dr. Ricardo A. Saracco Álvarez as Editor-in-Chief. Dr. Jesús A. Aldana López serves as Administrative Editor, and Dr. Francisco R. de la Peña serves as Scientific Editor. This initiative emerged following the passing of Dr. Rafael Medina Dávalos † to create a sustainable framework for the association's publication of applied literature. The board published the works scheduled for the latter half of 2024. It implemented a new editorial process that includes peer-review practices and a hybrid publication model integrating print editions with digital distribution.

Global Engagement

On the international front, the association organized the 24th World Congress of Psychiatry in collaboration with the World Psychiatric Association, under the presidency of Dr. Danuta Wasserman—the event took place from November 14 to 17, 2024, in Mexico City. The congress garnered 3,674 attendees from 90 countries (World Psychiatric Association, 2024). It also revitalized the academic commitments of the association's state chapters by promoting pedagogical activities for psychiatry trainees, early-career professionals, and active members.

Closing Remarks

Looking ahead, the Asociación Psiquiátrica Mexicana, A.C., is tasked with organizing the XXIX National Congress, scheduled for November 13–16 in Mérida, Yucatán. The current administration continues to strike a balance between institutional growth and scientific rigor, promoting initiatives to increase membership and raise mental health awareness through collaboration with governmental and private institutions. The organization of the 24th World Congress of Psychiatry exemplifies the association's global engagement and its ability to strengthen national networks (World Psychiatric Association, 2024). In 2025, the association aims to consolidate these advancements into a long-term strategy for psychiatric practice, education, and research.

References

- Crossref. (2024). The DOI® System: Ensuring Persistent Links to Scholarly Content. Crossref. From <https://www.crossref.org>
- International ISSN Centre. (2024). ISSN Services: Supporting The Global Identification of Serial Publications. International Centre for the Registration of Serial Publications. From <https://www.issn.org>
- World Psychiatric Association. (2024). 24th World Congress of Psychiatry: Scientific Program and Highlights. World Psychiatric Association. From <https://www.wpanet.org>

CC creative commons

